

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF IRREALIS

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Abstract:

In recent times, it has been observed that the linguistic significance of the confrontation between the concepts of realis and irrealis in linguistics is the subject of heated debate. The fact that the concept of irrealis has not been fully and widely studied and clearly described suggests the need for a comparative-typological comprehensive study of this phenomenon. Currently, the fact that irrealis is not yet given the status of an autonomous semantic category causes controversy among linguists. Semantic proportionality of the irrealis concept assumes learning by analyzing in most irrealis constructions (hypothetical-shart sentences, opposite conditions, side-click conditions, optatives, commands, alternative relations).

Key words: alternative relation, hypothesis, irrealis, optative device, prototypic aspect, potential phenomenon.

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In our developing country, the emphasis on linguistics is increasing day by day. The fact that the hypothesis exists is linked to a series of concepts commonly referred to as irrealis supports the hypothesis put forward by Mauri. He proposes to include hypothetical, assumptions in the content encoding alternative relationships among irrealis characters.

The author notes that "...the irrealis sign is defined as a hypothetical, assumed eventuality of indicators that directly encode the irrealis state of the relevant situational expression or encode a concept that implies nonreality. The final characteristic of Irrealis indicators also includes conceptual coding. Because they encode a concept that implies an unrealized state of situational expressions.

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In the example above, two or more distinct irrealis denoting situational expressions representing incompatible alternatives are united into one conceptual system. However, in linguistic comparison, the epistemic communication relations of irrealis indicators, as well as the conceptualization of irrealis, may not be the same. "It's probably just as well", she said. She would be for more comfortable dealing with Erastus, who under normal circumstances could be relied upon to be at least somewhat reasonable (Susan Law, 43): if she continued to fire an unhappy wife, I would have been whispered like a kebab in the oven (G'.G'ulam, 131). Probably in the English example has served as a

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reference to predicates with irrealis content, which means the next sentences in the text. The Irrealis meaning would be for, could be relied upon predicates are harmonised with the grammatical form. In the example of the Uzbek language, however, the use of the condition *mile* has produced an irrealis associated with the speech situation. In this, irrealis-*sa*, - *ar* was performed using grammatical suffixes.

The use of irrealis in conditional adverbial clauses implies an alternative alternative adverbial adverb in a certain sense. When the choice of alternative is derived from the point of view of human intents, we can judge that it is an existential part of conceptual activity.

"The situational expression to be presented as an alternative must be described in terms of opportunity with already existing irrealis signs". In other words, not only subtractive binders, but also irrealis characters serve to present two or more situational expressions as alternatives.

Of course, the irrealis in conditional follow-up sentences serves to link the relationship between separator connectives on the one hand and irrealis characters on the other. The condition is expressed as an alternative due to the description of the situation defined (or linked) in sentences in terms of "Opportunity" (s) of expressions. In this case, the selectable alternative is presented as mutually exclusive options. This correlation is supported by the analysis of each language, indicating that "many of the binders that encode an alternative are indeed derived or evolved from irrealis characters".

Given this conceptual complexity, it should be taken into account that, like encoding modality in languages, there are the same complexities in encoding Irrealis. For example, when a language can allocate its maximally undefined characters to an inactivated expression, it does not matter what the specifics of the reality being expressed are.

We have proposed above that a series of constructions that represent irrealis concepts, such as conditional, recommendations and optatives, conveys the conclusion that conditional or the facticity of the stated situational expression is an undeniable option, among others. Disjunctive constructions explicitly encode the existence of a set of mutually exclusive variants. In these constructions, the subtractor determines that the binders are not excluded from one option in their scope. They can therefore be considered conditional as signs of the probabilities of the fact, equivalent to (some) optatives and (some) advisory signs.

Communicative use of fact probability which gives the content of irrealis.

As mentioned above, J. One argument used by bayby against the autonomy of Irrealis is that the concept of irrealis has little communicative significance. By dividing the concept of Irrealis into three other specific concepts of contrafactuality, probability of fact, and noneferentiality, we can raise the issue of communicative use of each of these concepts, rather than the concept of total absence of reality.

Focusing on the probabilities of the fact, we can ask what may be the communicative purpose of showing the situational expression as belonging to a set of mutually exclusive situations. We propose that the probability of fact has the function of introducing the expression of the situation into speech, as a result of which we achieve that the speaker is not attracted to the loyalty to the truth of the statements that characterize them. In other words, the probability of the fact serves to suspend the speaker's commitment to what he is saying. This

communicative function must be defined in some way, since even a simple statement means that the speaker is faithful to what he says. As Morency wrote: "We can emphasize that when a speaker expresses the content of P in the form of a statement, he expresses his commitment to P: otherwise, it will lead to logical inconsistency."

Suspension of obligations is a very important communicative function. This is logically necessary for the functioning of hypotheses, preferences and alternative relationships, and logically is hidden in optatives and rhetorically useful for recommendations. In addition, the suspension of commitment can also be used to conclude that the speaker is not fully committed to the truth he or she is telling, that is, it can be used to draw conclusions about the speaker's epistemic attitude.

From the opinions and considerations mentioned above, it can be concluded that modality and irrealis serve very different purposes. In particular, modality presupposes and classifies the speaker's commitment. Irrealis, on the other hand, demonstrates hypothetical purpose, probable hypotheses, rather than the speaker's obligation to carry out an action.

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